

Accurate prediction on COVID-19 vaccination's effectiveness in the past

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ABSTRACT

In January 2020, the author found that it would be difficult or impossible for a COVID-19 vaccine to prevent future COVID-19 infections due to the morphological and structural characteristics of SARS-COV-2. Mass vaccination without regard to timing would impose a heavy burden on the governments. At the same cost, the timing of vaccination becomes more critical. How to give citizens the longest protection period and the best protection after vaccination under safe conditions is a question that should be considered when implementing vaccination. Even 90% of the population has completed vaccination, thus achieving the original concept of herd immunity. However, once active physical isolation and social distancing controls are abandoned, approximately 10 - 70% or more infections may occur in. A month before the Tokyo Olympics, the author published an article with related comments in a preprint, and the current global epidemic situation is as he expected in the past. The significance and economic value of large-scale COVID-19 vaccination should be reconsidered by policymakers.

Keywords: SARS-COV-2 · novel coronavirus · COVID-19 · vaccine · vaccination · herd immunity · prediction · prospective · health policy · pharmacobehavioral economics · health behavioral economics · strategy

In January 2020, the author found that it would be difficult or impossible for the COVID-19 vaccine to prevent future COVID-19 infections and that unexpected adverse reactions could occur¹⁻³. Mass vaccination without considering the timing does not conform to the principles of medical behavioral economics, and the government will bear a heavy burden. An article on related points was placed in the preprint version of the paper a month before the Tokyo Olympics, and now the results are as expected by the author. As of May 12, 2022, the country reported a cumulative 3.358576 billion doses of COVID-19 vaccine⁴, with a total number of 1.287195 billion vaccinations. 1.252592 billion people have been vaccinated in the whole process, accounting for 91.3% and 88.85% of the country's total population, respectively.

However, in some cities, the COVID-19 infection rate has exceeded 50 percent within half a month after China adopted a lying flat policy. The total population of

Henan Province in 2022 is about 99.366 million. As of January 6, 2023, the infection rate of COVID-19 in Henan was 89.0%, including 89.1% in urban areas and 88.9% in rural areas⁵, the provincial People's Government Information Office announced on Jan 9. At this stage, the epidemic strain is still dominated by the variant of Omikron BA.5.2. As of 7 January 2023, 13.722 million people aged 60 - 79 had been vaccinated in the province, for a vaccination rate of 98.49%, and 10.0863 million had been strengthened, for a vaccination rate of 93.58%. 1.5498 million people over the age of 80 years were vaccinated throughout the process, with a vaccination rate of 93.25%, and 0.9082 million were strengthened, with a vaccination rate of 80.27%. The previously anticipated views are shared as follows.

Morphological and structural features of SARS-CoV-2 lead to easy mutation

Vaccination with the COVID-19 vaccine is a very important means to combat the novel coronavirus epidemic. However, some people in at-risk areas are afraid to get vaccinated because of rare severe coagulation reaction or deaths after receiving the COVID-19 vaccine⁶. Some members of the public refused vaccination. Moreover, due to the morphological and structural characteristics of SARS-CoV-2, the virus is prone to mutation and strong disease-causing mutants may occur from time to time. Normally, fresh vaccine re-modified with the variant strain can be marketed at least 3 months later than the emergence of the variant strain, while the variant strain may infect a larger range of people and have a more serious impact. At the WHO press conference on June 14, 2021, Director General Dr Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus mentioned that the mutated SARS-CoV-2 has accelerated the spread of the pandemic globally⁷. The current spread of the novel coronavirus has outpaced the speed of vaccine distribution. All of this means that even though the majority of people in the world have been vaccinated against COVID-19, there may still be ongoing SARS-CoV-2 infection. Without the emergence of unexpectedly effective drugs in most countries around the world, if the COVID-19 prevention and control strategy of most countries in the world is not able to progress rapidly, the 2020 Tokyo Olympic Games may not be held properly as in the past until next year, even if postponed again (The Games will have to be held this year because of concerns about the sports industry, sportsmanship, economy and politics, etc., but there may be few live audiences), and the road to global economic recovery this year will not be smoothly.

The timing of vaccination

Now, many countries around the world are implementing national vaccination programs for the public in hopes of quickly gaining herd immunity. However, some countries, regions or the international community may neglect the issue of vaccinating the public within the region at a proper time and at a lower cost. Currently, volunteers or organizers have repeatedly urged the public to get vaccinated in areas of some countries where there have been virtually no new COVID-19 cases for seven or eight months or more than a year. Due to the limited production capacity of the vaccine, the increasing number of mutant strains, the limited period of protection after vaccination,

and the need to continue to vaccinate after expiration, at the same cost, the timing of vaccination becomes more crucial. How to make the public obtain the longest protection period and the best protection after vaccination in a safe situation should be considered in the implementation of vaccination. Otherwise, it could lead to a waste of vaccine resources and an excessive medical burden on the government. If large numbers of people remain infected with the mutated virus after vaccination, public confidence and desire for vaccination could be affected. Therefore, we suggest that vaccination strategies should be implemented in different regions, grades, groups and time periods based on control patterns, new confirmed cases, existing risk levels, mobility of people, and input status of high and low risk areas in the country or region. In this way, the epidemic prevention funds can be disbursed in stages and managed reasonably, so as to reduce the pressure on the epidemic prevention funds in the short term, prevent more people from being infected with less cost and achieve better social benefits, which should be more in line with the principles of health behavioral economics. In addition, the significance and economic value of large-scale COVID-19 vaccination should be reconsidered by policymakers.

10-70% or more infections may still occur after the number of mass immunization achieved

Due to the morphological characteristics of the novel coronavirus, mutant strains with stronger pathogenic capacity are prone to appear. The authors predict that, depending on the currently widely implemented defenses, even 90% of the population in a large number of countries or regions has completed vaccination, achieving the original idea of herd immunity. However, in at-risk areas, once active physical isolation and social distancing controls are abandoned, approximately 10 - 70% or more of infections are likely to occur in this area after exposure to more pathogenic mutant strains, otherwise immunity may be completely broken down. This means that prevention and control policies and measures for imported cases in a country or region may not be relaxed for a certain period of time. In China, the pace of COVID-19 vaccination has been too fast, the vaccination population has been too large in a short period of time, and there are no plans to delay vaccination by divisions or groups. It is likely that it will fall into a passive situation for some time in the future.

Competent people should be promoted to an appropriate core position and implement all harmless and effective means

According to the author, the current global COVID-19 pandemic is not being controlled effectively, and politicization is a major reason. Second, senior officials in some countries lack the ability to transfer experience. Third, large amounts of money are being invested in vaccination, which is the wrong direction or selective, and will increase the burden of health insurance in most countries. The variability of the novel coronavirus has led to the fact that the COVID-19 vaccine has become the vaccine of choice for the reduction of severe patients rather than the conventional vaccine, which will significantly increase the cost of control. This is inconsistent with the principles

of pharmacobehavioral economics or health behavioral economics or health behavioral management. The author and his family members have not vaccinated with the COVID-19 vaccine since the 2019 pandemic. Although the author has often been exposed to a large number of positive cases, they have never been positive or infected with COVID-19.

The author believes that relying on the existing discovery and medical technology is enough to control the global epidemic. The key is to promote capable people to appropriate core positions, so that all harmless and effective means can be quickly implemented in an emergency. In the absence of effective measures, it would be wrong to remove physical defenses and coexist with the virus for a long time, which would inevitably lead to more infections and deaths, while disturbing people's hearts or minds. The vast majority of the public have no medical background or effective measures, but the public is easily influenced by the speeches of people of status. In the absence of effective measures, it has been proposed to remove physical defenses and coexist with the virus for a long time. In fact, this shows that the proposers themselves do not see the prospect that intractable problems can be solved quickly and efficiently, and that breakthroughs cannot be found. They did not see the serious consequences of this strategy, though they needed only a simple calculation.

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